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RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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Disclaimer

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Table of Contents

1 Contents

Abstract	7
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1 Context.....	8
1.2 Scope and Goals.....	8
1.3 Document Structure.....	10
2 Field work preparation procedures and guidelines	11
2.1 Available Infrastructure	11
2.1.1 Instruments.....	11
2.1.2 Vehicles.....	13
2.2 Deployment scenarios	14
2.2.1 Full RAMONES system deployment.....	14
2.3 Deployment of RAMONES robotic vehicles alone	15
3 Experiments at Milos, Greece	17
3.1 Area of work.....	17
3.1.1 Relevant data.....	18
3.2 Participants	19
3.3 ROV-based measurements	20
3.3.1 Deployment at Paleochori beach	21
3.3.2 Deployment at Alykes beach	22
3.4 Handheld γ Sniffer measurements	22
3.5 Concurrent measurements and physical sampling.....	24
3.5.1 Physical sampling.....	24
3.6 Preliminary Results	26
3.6.1 γ Sniffer.....	26
3.6.2 SUGI	34
3.6.3 Physical sampling.....	36
3.6.4 Field calibration of γ Sniffers	41
4 Experiments at Kolumbo	44
4.1 Area of work.....	44

4.2	Participants	46
4.3	Experiments / Infrastructure	46
4.4	ROV based measurements.....	46
4.5	Preliminary Results	47
4.5.1	First Kolumbo expedition.....	47
4.5.2	Second Kolumbo expedition	49
5	Gliders Experiments at Portugal.....	53
6	Conclusions.....	56

Abstract

This report provides an overview of the field campaigns of RAMONES for testing, validating, and collecting data from the instruments that have been developed at that time.

Field operations were held in Milos shallow water hydrothermal fields on 24 - 30 of March 2023 and twice in Kolumbo deep hydrothermal vent field on 12-15 June 2023 and 20-25 October 2023. Moreover, engineering tests of the modified underwater glider and the acoustic communication and positioning system were performed at Castelo de Bode Dam reservoir lake, Portugal during the week of September 18 to 22, 2023.

These included:

- Engineering tests for three γ Sniffers, SUGI, CHERI UV camera, and the control unit of Benthic Lab that have been developed in RAMONES.
- Physical sampling from different areas for establishing background radiation levels.
- Concurrent in water measurements with the RAMONES instruments and physical sampling (gas & sediment) for laboratory measurements, to help characterise the instruments.
- Autonomous underwater glider dynamics testing in a real environment.
- Acoustic communications and positioning with the new systems integration.

Preliminary results suggest that the instruments operate as expected and that they are sensitive enough to distinguish radioactivity gradients in the water in an approximate range up to 1 m. Moreover, glider dynamics show to be in-line with the specifications after the integration of the acoustic systems and the γ Sniffer.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

This report is the deliverable D3.2 “Coastal-water sites experiments” of the H2020 FET PROACTIVE RAMONES project. The report is a product of the field experiments as defined in WP3 “Onsite Integration, Testing and Pilot Demonstrators”. Four field experiments were performed until M36. The first was conducted in March 2023 in the coastal zone of Milos, Greece where active hydrothermal fields are present. The next two deployments were jointly organized with the sister research project SANTORY at the Kolumbo submarine volcano at the NE of Santorini, Greece the first of them in June and the second in October 2023. The last experiment was for testing the modified autonomous underwater gliders in a lake in Portugal.

1.2 Scope and Goals

This report provides an overview of the field campaigns of RAMONES for testing and validating the instruments and the robotic platforms that have been developed in the context of RAMONES.

Milos, Greece

Field operations were held in Milos shallow water hydrothermal fields on 24 - 30 of March 2023. These included:

- Engineering tests for two γ Sniffers, SUGI, CHERI UV camera, and the control unit of Benthic Lab that have been developed in RAMONES.
- Sampling from different areas for establishing background radiation levels.
- Concurrent in water measurements with the RAMONES instruments and physical sampling (gas & sediment) for laboratory measurements, to help characterize the instruments.

The main goal of this field campaign was to establish the levels of activity, to determine if sensors are sensitive for a full-fledged deployment that is useful for monitoring a natural system, or if technology needs development to decrease detection levels, and/or adapt the strategy of monitoring.

Kolumbo submarine volcano, Santorini, Greece

Under the frame of GR/HFRI SANTORY project (MoU with RAMONES), field operations were held at Kolumbo submarine volcano (Santorini, Greece), during the Thira23 Kolumbo Expedition in 12-15 June 2023 aboard the R/V Aegeo, and Thira23 Kolumbo Expedition in 20-25 October 2023 aboard the R/V Filia. During these expeditions engineering tests and data collection of natural radioactivity were performed using the γ Sniffers, the SUGI and the CHERI UV camera.

The experiments performed on Milos and Kolumbo will help address the following open questions/issues:

- Characterize radioactivity levels and radionuclides (both in situ or at lab) in:
 - a) sediment
 - b) water
 - c) complemented with land-based measurements

- Quantify unknown parameters:
 - Detection level of instruments
 - ❖ Which signals of interest can be measured
 - ❖ What is the minimum integration time for detecting them
 - ❖ Which are the proper settings
 - ❖ Which signal thresholds will be used as indicators
 - ❖ Based on integration times: glider flight strategy or fix point monitoring (longer integration times)

- Reconnaissance of field area for future instrument deployments (activity vs. sensitivity of instruments). Is Milos, and Paleochori bay in particular, suitable for RAMONES demonstration pilots with gliders (e.g., measure steadily increased radioactivity as the gliders approaches the coastline)

- Compare measurement subaerially

- Structural characterization of instrumented seeps:
 - ❖ Types of structures (e.g. faults, fractures, fractured corridor)
 - ❖ Structural attributes (e.g. strike, dip, length, aperture)
 - ❖ Structural location (e.g. in relation to the fault, to the graben)
 - ❖ Relations with the aquifer, the volcanic centres, the regional tectonics

- Signature of natural systems (sources, mixing, etc)
 - ❖ sampling locally (vents vs. outside vents)
 - ❖ sampling regionally -> zones w/ venting vs. no venting

Overall, the plan was to test RAMONES instruments (γ Sniffers, SUGI, CHERI UV) in a real environment to help address the above questions and estimate/measure background radiation levels (with standard sampling) in a known active vent field area for correlation with RAMONES instruments.

Castelo de Bode Dam reservoir lake, Portugal

In addition, engineering tests have been performed at Castelo de Bode Dam reservoir in Portugal for the validation of the customized autonomous underwater glider vehicles that are fitted with the EVOL acoustic communications systems and a γ Sniffer.

1.3 Document Structure

Section 2 provides an overview of the instrument and vehicle preparation procedures for field deployment, Section 3 discusses in detail the experiments performed in the island of Milos, Greece, covering both the preparation and the results of the expedition. Section 4 presents the experiments performed during the two expeditions at the submarine volcano of Kolumbo in the NE part of Santorini, Greece, and Section 5 presents the integration sessions and tests that took place in Lisbon, Portugal, regarding the RAMONES underwater gliders. Finally, Section 6 concludes this deliverable.

2 Field work preparation procedures and guidelines

This section summarizes the field work preparation procedures that have been established in the context of the RAMONES project. It provides general guidelines for the correct preparation of the developed instruments and robotic vehicles before performing radioactivity measurements both in coastal zones and deep water. It also summarizes the possible deployment scenarios and the operations that take place during the deployment of the RAMONES system, according to the radioactivity mapping objectives.

2.1 Available Infrastructure

The following instruments and assets were prepared for the field tests at Milos.

2.1.1 Instruments

γ Sniffers (Figure 1)

- CdZnTe gamma radiation detection
- 4cm³ crystal
- Depth rating 500 m
- Stand-alone operation from ROV, gliders or on benthic lab
- On-line operation via connection to Laptop via USB
- Custom software in ROS for data logging

Figure 1: Maritized γ Sniffer instrument, next to a regular pen for size comparison

SUGI (Figure 2)

- Radioactivity imaging instrument
- Depth rating 500m
- Four 4cm³ CdZnTe crystals
- 11x11 pixelated detector modules (+ cathode)
- 14-bit ADC converters
- Event-by-event analysis
- Standalone deployment from ROV or from benthic lab
- On-line operation via connection to Laptop via Ethernet

Figure 2: Electronics of the benthic lab (left) connected to the SUGI sensor (right), both mounted on 3D printed bases and the caps of their underwater housings

CHERI UV imaging (Figure 3)

- Based on ultra-sensitive UV CCD camera
- Depth rating 500m
- Dome port

Figure 3: UV imaging instrument inside an underwater housing with dome end

Bentic Lab (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Electronics of the benthic lab, connected to a γ Sniffer instrument

2.1.2 Vehicles

ROV “METIS” (Figure 5)

Figure 5: ROV METIS tested inside a pool, with a γ Sniffer and SUGI mounted on it

RAMONES underwater gliders (Figure 6)

Figure 6: Ballasting of RAMONES glider in pool

RAMONES (ROC-SIANI) A-Tirma G3 Sail-drone (Figure 7)

Figure 7: ROC-SIANI A-Tirma G3 Sail-drone

2.2 Deployment scenarios

We now visit the foreseen deployment scenarios of the RAMONES assets. The main differentiating factor among the scenarios is the presence of the benthic lab. We envision two different scenarios.

2.2.1 Full RAMONES system deployment

In this scenario all RAMONES assets are deployed (see Figure 8). These include the autonomous underwater gliders (AUGs) equipped with γ Sniffers, the unmanned surface vehicle (USV) SailDrone possibly also equipped with a γ Sniffer for measuring radioactivity near the surface, and the benthic lab that hosts the CHERI, SUGI, aSPECT and GASPARG instruments.

This scenario is relevant when high radioactivity concentrations are suspected in the proximity of a well-defined geographical location. In this case, the benthic lab can be deployed first, collecting valuable information with its radioactivity detection and the imaging instruments. Based on these data, areas of interest can be defined for the gliders to scan with their γ Sniffers in a collaborative manner. The data from the gliders are transferred to the surface vehicle where they are aggregated and used to build an online map of radioactivity, which can be subsequently used to update the extent of the area of interest.

Figure 8: RAMONES system deployment considering all assets

2.3 Deployment of RAMONES robotic vehicles alone

In this scenario a, possibly broad, area of interest is defined for radioactivity mapping with the RAMONES robotic vehicles alone (Figure 9). In the initial phase, a volume of interest is defined for radioactivity mapping in a suitable coordinate references system, typically WGS84 geographical coordinates or a national reference system (e.g. GGRS87 in Greece). The gliders collect radioactivity measurements in the area of interest and a map of the radioactivity distribution is reconstructed on-line using the aggregated data on board of the surface vehicle. Based on this provisional radioactivity map, the area of interest can be updated in an informed manner, redirecting the gliders towards locations where higher concentrations are suspected. This scenario can also trigger the use of the benthic lab if a location with particular interest regarding radioactivity concentration is detected.

Figure 9: RAMONES system deployment scenario without the benthic lab

3 Experiments at Milos, Greece

Field experiments were performed in the island of Milos, Greece from the 25th to the 30th of March 2023. Radioactivity measurements with the γ Sniffer and the SUGI instruments mounted on a mini ROV have been collected from the hydrothermal fields at the Paleochori and Alykes beaches (Figure 10), while coast-based measurements and physical sampling were performed in various coastal locations of interest around the island.

Figure 10: Map of Milos Island (Greece) where the field deployment sites are indicated

3.1 Area of work

Milos is the south-western edge of the Cyclades islands in the Aegean Sea, Greece, and the largest island of Milos volcanic complex. It is located at the NW part of the modern active Aegean Volcanic Arc, an area characterized by intense volcano-tectonic activity. Volcanism in Milos initiated 3.5 million years ago, covering almost the entire island with volcanic products and continued up to 80 thousand years ago.

The neotectonic configuration of Milos is complex, with uplifting or subsiding blocks and even tilting or rotations around inclined axes. The most dominant tectonic features, which have configured the overall morphology of the island, are two major fault zones bounding the central block of Milos – Fyriplaka tectonic graben (MFTG).

Faults bounding the fault blocks of the island have served as conduits for geothermal fluids resulting in alterations of the adjacent volcano-sedimentary formations, giving rise to a

spectrum of exploitable industrial mineral and hydrothermal deposit types on-land, and exploited since the antiquity.

These hydrothermal manifestations do occur also underwater, extending from the shore to depths of 500 m or more, although the submarine hydrothermal system around the island is not fully mapped. Thus, today Milos constitutes a preserved onshore and offshore laboratory to study hydrothermal processes. In the near-shore environment, the most intense hydrothermal venting activity (0–15 m water depth) is located along the SE coastline at Paleochori Bay corresponding with the prolongation of the eastern marginal fault of the Milos – Fyriplaka neotectonic graben, which hosts the Fyriplaka subaerial volcano.

Here the distribution of hydrothermal outflow, temperatures of the seafloor, and association with bacterial and other microbial communities has been studied in recent times by members of Ramones Project, and thus provides a natural laboratory to a) evaluate the levels of natural radioactivity both associated with the hydrothermal outflow underwater, and away from it, and b) test instrumentation and evaluate deployment techniques adapted for environmental monitoring underwater.

3.1.1 Relevant data

Figure 11: Geodynamic position of Milos within the Hellenic Volcanic Arc (After Nomikou et al., 2013.)

Figure 12: Map showing the neotectonic configuration of Milos (After Papanikolaou et al., 1990).

3.2 Participants

Table 1: List of people participating in the experiments at Milos, Greece

Person	Partner	Dates	Role
BEJELOU Konstantina	NKUA	25/3/ - 31/3	Physical sampling
MERTZIMEKIS Theodoros	NKUA	24/3 - 30/3	Instruments characterization
MADESIS Ioannis	NKUA	26/3 - 30/3	Instruments characterization
SILTZOVALIS Georgios	NKUA	24/3 - 27/3	Instruments characterization
NOMIKOU Paraskevi	NKUA	27/3 - 30/3	Physical sampling
ANAGNOSTOU Eirini	NKUA	27/3 - 30/3	Physical sampling
BRETON Vincent	UCA/LPC ¹	25/3 - 31/3	Background levels Physical sampling

¹ Laboratoire de Physique de Clermont

CHARDON Patrick	UCA/LPC ¹	25/3 - 31/3	Background levels Physical sampling
TERRAY Luca	UCA/LPC ¹	25/3 - 31/3	Background levels Physical sampling
MAIGNE Lydia	UCA/LPC ¹	25/3 - 31/3	Background levels Physical sampling
MALLIOS Angelos	PLOA	24/3 – 28/3	Instruments operation/testing
VLASSOPOULOS Othonas	PLOA	24/3 – 28/3	ROV piloting
CABECINHAS David	IST-ID	24/3 - 31/3	Instruments operation/testing
KARANTZALOS Konstantinos	NTUA	24/3 - 28-3	Instruments operation/testing
NTOUSKOS Makis	NTUA	24/3 – 28/3	Instruments operation/testing
ANTONIOU Christos	NTUA	24/3 – 28/3	Instruments operation/testing
SPANOS Sotiris	NTUA	24/3 – 28/3	Instruments operation/testing
AUGER Sylvain	U. Lyon	27/3 - 3/4	SANTORY collaborative project
GRANDJEAN Philippe	U. Lyon	27/3/ - 3/4	SANTORY collaborative project
MARTELAT Jean Emmanuel	U. Lyon	27/3 - 3/4	SANTORY collaborative project
CAVAILLHES Thibaut	U. Bordeaux	27/3 - 31/3	SANTORY collaborative project

3.3 ROV-based measurements

Engineering tests of the instruments were performed on the 24th and the 25th of March. The “METIS” ROV was used as a carrier vehicle for facilitating measurements in different depths, as well as to simulate gliders’ spatial displacement motion.

The γ Sniffer, SUGI, and CHERI UV Camera were connected to the control module of the Benthic lab, and the last one was connected to the ROV via Gigabit Ethernet. That way, there was real-time control and data through the ROV’s fiber optic umbilical to the support craft.

Both SUGI and γ Sniffer have been mounted on a mini ROV at nearby positions and at the same height with respect to the ROV frame (Figure 13). During the experiments, the ROV visited multiple gas emitting sources (vents), collecting radioactivity measurements at different depths and distances from the vents, in order to estimate radioactivity levels in the water column and on the sea bottom.

Figure 13: SUGI and γ Sniffer instruments mounted on the ROV. The blue tapes in the inset image indicate the orientation of the detector modules at the ROV bottom side.

3.3.1 Deployment at Paleochori beach

Field tests at Paleochori beach took place from the 25th to the 26th of March 2023. This location presents confirmed underwater sources of radioactivity, mainly daughter products of ^{222}Rn contained in the gaseous vent emissions. Both instruments (SUGI and γ Sniffer) were used to measure the radioactivity above active hydrothermal vents, visually identified by the presence of bubbles as well as discolorations of the seabed (Figure 14).

The first day was dedicated to engineering tests and qualitative control of the instrument readings executed by standing on the seabed with the ROV for some seconds and then slowly ascending until reaching the surface. On the second day, more detailed tests were executed, both using the touch-stay-and-rise setting described above, as well as slowly traversing the suspected sources horizontally at different depths, to examine the distribution of radioactivity around the sources.

Figure 14 Left: GPS track of the boat from which the ROV was deployed and area with hydrothermal vents visited with the ROV; Right: View from the ROV camera on top of a source where seabed discoloration is also evident

3.3.2 Deployment at Alykes beach

On the 26th of March of field experiments, we collected measurements at Alykes. For these experiments we used the ROV as a benthic station, anchoring it on the seabed for five minutes, collecting measurements each time at different positions on a circular pattern with a radius of about half a meter around a very active vent in shallow waters (around 1 meter depth, see Figure 15). This experiment was conducted to validate the difference between background measurements, the measurements right above the source and those around it.

Figure 15 Left: Location of hydrothermal vent studied at Alykes beach; Right: View from the ROV camera at Alykes where high degassing activity is observed

3.4 Handheld γ Sniffer measurements

A number of measurements was performed during the Milos field campaign, using the handheld γ Sniffers. Points of interest include both places with observed activity, and lack of activity. The goal behind these measurements is to acquire experimental data, under realistic environmental conditions, to feed the field-based calibration of the γ Sniffers. The measuring setup used during the handheld measurements, included the CZT sensor encapsulated inside a waterproof housing. To achieve stability in the position of the sensor during the underwater measurements, as it was placed near the coastline, a small anchor (~5 kg) was tied with it, see figure 16 (right). In the following map, all in-situ measurements using the handheld γ Sniffers are depicted. Details for each measurement are provided in the tables below.

Figure 16: (Left) Location of in-situ measurements on the island of Milos. (Right) One of the handheld γ Sniffers ready for deployment in shallow waters.

Table 2: Summary of in-situ measurements.

Location	Latitude (deg.)	Longitude (deg.)	Detector S/N	Interval (sec)	# of intervals	Duration (sec)	Notes
Paleochori (M5)	36.674983	24.520162	278	3600	1	3600	sand
Paleochori (WaterM6)	36.674801	24.52007	278	1461	1	1461	water
Paleochori (M7)	36.675062	24.519288	278	3600	1	3600	sand
Alykes (M14)	36.674182	24.513285	278	3600	1	3600	water
Alykes (M14)	36.674182	24.513285	279	3600	1	3600	water
AgiaKiriaki	36.668318	24.495804	278	3600	1	3600	water
AgiaKiriaki	36.668318	24.495804	279	3600	1	3600	water
Alykes	36.705959	24.470036	278	100	40	4000	water
Alykes	36.705959	24.470036	279	300	14	4200	water
Voudia	36.746715	24.532529	279	120	30	3600	water
Paleochori	36.674878	24.516185	279	120	31	3720	water
Paleochori	36.674878	24.516185	279	10	60	600	water
French cemetery	36.720946	24.436516	279	120	30	3600	swamp

3.5 Concurrent measurements and physical sampling

Certain in situ measurements using the handheld γ Sniffers were performed in the same locations from which samples were collected. The table below illustrates the pairing created.

Table 3: Pairing of in situ measurements and sample collection from the same location.

Location	Sample name	In situ measurement date
Voudia	M16	28.03.2023
Paleochori	HVF5, HVF6	29.03.2023
Agia Kiriaki	M12, M13	26.03.2023
Alykes	M14, M15	30.03.2023

The goal behind this pairing is to calibrate the response of the γ Sniffers using actual data collected under realistic environmental conditions.

3.5.1 Physical sampling

Extended sampling of sand and sediments was carried out aiming to contribute to the delineation of the radioactivity levels found in the island for specific radionuclides of interest. Regarding the HVF1-6 samples, these were obtained for both the NKUA and UCA groups. The HVF(1+2)(3+4)(5+6) are samples from the same place, where the odd measurements denote exactly at bubble activity, and even measurements 1 m away. In the following tables more information is presented regarding sampling locations, etc.

Figure 17: Sampling sites from Milos.

Table 4: Sampling conducted in Paleochori bay.

Sample name/location	Latitude (deg.)	Longitude (deg.)	Comment/Description
M1	36.674467	24.522104	Sand
M2	36.674335	24.522007	small pebbles
M3	36.674812	24.521172	Sand
M4	36.674664	24.521103	small pebbles
M5	36.674983	24.520162	sand, measured in situ on the beach
M6	36.674801	24.52007	sand, measured in situ inside water
M7	36.675062	24.519288	sand, measured in situ on the beach
M8	36.67498	24.519304	Sand
M9	36.675138	24.517508	Sand
M10	36.675064	24.517557	Sand
M11	36.675123	24.516355	Sand

Other than Paleochori, samples were acquired from other bays of the island, in order to have a systematic approach from every side of the island.

Table 5: Sampling from various locations in Milos.

Location	Sample name	Lat.	Long.	Comment/Description
Agia Kyriaki	M12	36.670916	24.498698	sand
Agia Kyriaki	M13	36.670867	24.498714	sand
Alykes bay	M14	36.705942	24.470275	sand
Alykes bay	M15	36.705003	24.470287	sand
Voudia	M16	36.746794	24.53244	small pebbles
Voudia	M17	36.747379	24.532788	small pebbles
Pachaina bay	M18	36.752712	24.497118	sand
French Cemetery	FC	36.720946	24.436516	mud

Additionally, we were able to also acquire sediments from Paleochori in three different locations. In each case, sediment was collected exactly from the HVF, and from 1 meter distance.

Table 6: Sampling conducted in Paleochori bay (29/3/2023).

Sample name	Lat.	Long.	Comment/Description
HVF1	36.674805	24.517391	water sediment (at bubbles)
HVF2	36.674805	24.517391	water sediment (at bubbles) (1 m from HVF1)

HVF3	36.674715	24.517136	water sediment (at bubbles)
HVF4	36.674715	24.517136	water sediment (at bubbles) (1 m from HVF3)
HVF5	36.674774	24.516098	water sediment (at bubbles)
HVF6	36.674774	24.516098	water sediment (at bubbles) (1 m from HVF5)

The samples were collected in sealed packaging of 1 to 1.5 kg, and transported to the laboratory. All collected samples were dried at 60 °C (varying times depending on the water content) and after that they were filtered using a 2mm gravel strainer. Once filtered, they were placed in standard 200 ml sealed PVC containers, and weighed with a 0.1 g mass precision. Afterward they were measured within the fully shielded HPGe detector of SERRES.

3.6 Preliminary Results

3.6.1 γ Sniffer

Data from the γ Sniffer deployed from the ROV were collected automatically using the developed ROS software module every 20 seconds with an acquisition time of 10 seconds (live time), resulting in separate SPE files containing the spectrum corresponding to the detection events registered in this time interval, together with meta-data regarding the setup of the detector and all relevant parameters. Preprocessing algorithms were developed to extract the data regarding detection events from the SPE files in relation to the UTC time of the acquisition and correlate them with measurement logs filled during the deployments as well as with the depth and other data regarding the status of the ROV. Figure 18 presents processed radioactivity measurements in terms of counts-per-second (CPS) vs UTC time considering different low-level discriminator (LLD) values for one of the deployments that took place on the second day of the field tests (26th of March), where four different vents, and thus radiation sources, were visited as can be seen by the elevated CPS values around 8:50, 9:25, 10:00 and 10:10. From Figure 19 to Figure 23 details of measurements collected at Paleochori using the γ Sniffer mounted on the ROV during the first two days are presented.

Figure 18: γ Sniffer measurements from a deployment at Paleochori beach for different LLD values

Figure 19: The diagram shows γ Sniffer measurements in total counts with 10 seconds integration time at source A, averaging 5.5 counts per second

Figure 20: γ Sniffer counts while the ROV performed a horizontal movement just above the seabed, counting 6.4 cps near source B and 5.8 cps near source C

Figure 21: γ Sniffer counts. In this experiment the ROV was ascending from the seabed

Figure 22: Counts from γ Sniffer from horizontally moving ROV traversing different sources/vents

Figure 23: Counts from γ Sniffer from horizontally moving ROV traversing different sources/vents

Similarly, Figure 24 shows the processed γ Sniffer data collected during the field deployment at Alykes beach on the 27th of March. In this graph annotations from the field log are showing, indicating different placements of the sensor around the vent being monitored.

Figure 24: Annotated γ Sniffer measurements from the Alykes beach for different LLD values

Figure 25 and 26 present the results for the handheld γ Sniffer (see relative Tables above for detector setup details). What happens in in-situ, underwater measurements is that due to the interaction of gamma rays with water, Compton scattering is orders of magnitude more present, therefore the majority of the registered events lies in lower energies, from 30 to 300 keV, as seen in the graphs. All spectra acquired were time normalized, since this is the format preferred for the γ Sniffers' principle of operation as well as for their exploitation to make feasible the instruments' calibration (mentioned in detail in section 3.6.4).

Figure 25: Time normalized spectra with energy axis in linear scale.

Figure 26: Time normalized spectra with energy axis in semi-log scale to emphasize the high Compton due to gamma scattering in the water volume

3.6.2 SUGI

The goal of the tests performed with SUGI was to validate the readings of the instrument via comparison with the measurements of the γ Sniffer. As stated above, different gas emitting sources (vents) have been visited with the ROV and radioactivity measurements were collected both at the seabed and at different water depths, to estimate radioactivity from the sediments and in the water column.

At Palaichori multiple radioactivity hot spots have been identified. Figure 27 shows the evolution of the count-per-second (CPS) values for both SUGI and γ Sniffer instruments for a continuous acquisition while the ROV visited four different sources in the study area designated in Figure 14, left. To compare the measurements event-by-event logs acquired by SUGI, CPS values have been calculated from considering a temporal window of 10 seconds, matching the configuration of the γ Sniffer. One can observe that the measurements taken from both instruments agree to a very high degree. Both instruments detected the same sources and indicated similar background radiation levels. Small differences can be attributed both to the differences in instrument efficiency, as well as differences due to their different placement on the ROV frame, exacerbated also by the significant radiation shielding of water as a sensor could be slightly closer to the source with respect to the other. Similar observations can be made on the data captured at Alykes (Figure 28).

Figure 27: Comparison of counts-per-second (CPS) readings from the baseline (γ Sniffer) sensor with CPS computed based on events registered by SUGI for Palaichori

Figure 28: Comparison of counts-per-second (CPS) readings from the baseline (γ Sniffer) sensor with CPS computed based on events registered by SUGI for Alykes

The joint SUGI and γ Sniffer experiments at Paleochori focused also on the dependence of radioactivity levels on the vertical distance from the source in the water. For this analysis, the touch-stay-and-rise manoeuvres were considered. In this setting, the CPS values computed based on the timestamped events registered by SUGI have been paired with the vertical distance from the sources (vents), computed based on the depth readings of the ROV. The results from different iterations are shown in. One can note that radioactivity readings are high when the ROV lies on the seabed while they return to background levels within less than 1 m distance.

Figure 29: Counts-per-second in relation to the vertical distance from the source

3.6.3 Physical sampling

The following maps depict the spatial distributions of the natural radioisotopes ^{228}Ra and ^{40}K , respectively based on physical samples taken from the locations indicated by a green circle. These radioisotopes are commonly used as tracers to understand geochemical dynamics in the marine environment. The developed thematic maps illustrate heat maps using a five-color code—no risk, normal, low risk, high risk, and eminent risk.

Figure 30: ^{228}Ra spatial distribution at Paleochori (Southern Milos) sampling areas. Basemap source: ESRI

Figure 31: ⁴⁰K spatial distribution at Paleochori (Southern Milos) sampling areas. Basemap source: ESRI

Figure 32: The fully-shielded HPGe detector used for γ -spectroscopy analysis of the samples

All samples were measured in a HPGe detector of 40% relative efficiency and superior energy resolution (0.21% at 662 keV) for long acquisition times, at least 80000 s, to acquire adequate statistics. The dead time of all measurements was very short (average dead time was 0.02%). The HPGe detector has coaxial geometry and a cylindrical crystal (\varnothing 60.5 mm x 63.3 mm). Its shielding is composed of lead and copper (\varnothing 52 cm, d=12 cm) thus being ideal for low count rate measurements of environmental radioactivity. Prior to sample analysis, a spectrum was

obtained without any sample inside the spectrometer to be used for background subtraction (Fig. 32). Once every line of the measured spectrum was identified and quantified, they were compared with reference samples (see Figs. 33b and 33c) of identical geometry and known activity to extract the specific activities of the Milos samples.

Analysis of each sample was performed with the aid of reference samples of the same bulk geometry. In total, two reference samples were used, one provided by IAEA and one by IRSN (see Figs. 33b and 33c). The IAEA reference provides known specific activity values for the ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs radionuclides, while the IRSN reference for ^{226}Ra and ^{228}Ra . The procedure followed for each sample collected from Milos is the following:

1. Initially, both the reference samples and the ones under analysis were background corrected and time normalized (extract cps)
2. A cross-check was performed between the reference sample and each one under investigation by examining the rate of the net area of the photopeaks of interest.
3. In particular for ^{40}K the peak at 1460.82 keV, for ^{226}Ra the peak at 186.21 keV and finally for ^{228}Ra the peak at 911.20 keV were chosen.
4. The uncertainties following the specific activities calculations were extracted via error propagation throughout the entire procedure. More specifically, uncertainties from the mass weighing of the sample, the specific activity value provided by the supplier of the reference sample and finally from the peak area calculation during the spectroscopy analysis (both in reference and investigated sample)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 33: Spectra obtained from the HPGe detector, (a) background for 80'000 s, (b) IAEA Reference Sample Material for 82'000 s and (c) IRSN Reference sample material for 80'000 s.

Figure 34: Spectrum acquired from the measurement of the HVF2 sample for a total acquisition time of 80'000 s

Figure 35: Specific activity of ⁴⁰K calculated for each sample collected

Figure 36: Specific activity of ²²⁶Ra calculated for each sample collected

Figure 37: Specific activity of ^{228}Ra calculated for each sample collected

The highest activity values for all three radionuclides examined were found in samples M14 and M15. Both of them were collected from the bay of Alykes, an area that gave us visible justification of hydrothermal activity.

3.6.4 Field calibration of γ Sniffers

Since the γ Sniffers will operate aboard gliders moving underwater with a certain speed, the data acquisition time should be kept as short as possible to preserve good spatial resolution during the source identification/localization process. More specifically, considering that a glider maintains a minimum velocity of approximately 20 cm/s, an integration period of 10 s yields a spatial resolution of 2 m. Therefore, the exceedingly brief integration time underwater is anticipated to impact the statistical outcomes of every measurement. As a result, the γ Sniffers will not perform spectroscopy but instead will utilize the variation of the total count rate registered by the CdZnTe-based spectrometer. So, in order to calibrate the instruments, results from in situ measurements with the handheld γ Sniffers and sample analysis using a HPGe detector in the laboratory were combined. As mentioned earlier in this deliverable a pairing was created between in situ measurements and sample collection carried out at the same location on Milos (see Table 3). The calibration procedure can be divided in steps, as follows:

1. The first step was to correlate the response (integrated count rate at the energy interval from 0 to 1500 keV) of the HPGe detector with the total specific activity determined for the respective sample (this determination was facilitated using reference samples). It is important to emphasize that in calculating the total specific activity values, we accounted for contributions from the isotopes ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra and ^{228}Ra . Figure 38a depicts the resulting calculated values. Subsequently, a linear fitting was executed on the experimental data (highlighted by the red line). The fitting equation is as follows:

$$\text{Total Specific Activity} = (183.7 \pm 35.3) \times \text{CPS HPGe} + (8.1 \pm 68.7) \quad (1)$$

- Subsequently, we proceeded to correlate the response (integrated count rate within the energy range from 0 to 1500 keV) of the two instruments—the γ Sniffer from in-situ measurements and HPGe from sample analysis. The resulting ratios (γ Sniffer over HPGe) were then plotted against the specific activity of the corresponding sample. Employing an appropriate fit (denoted by the red line in Figure 38b), we observed an absence of dependence of the studied ratio (y -axis) on the total specific activity value (x -axis). Moreover, the 95% confidence bands are depicted in the same figure as light green curved lines. The fitting equation is as follows:

$$\text{Ratio (Gamma Sniffer/HPGe)} = 3.02 \pm 0.41 \quad (2)$$

- The ultimate stage of calibration involves establishing the relationship between the response of the γ Sniffer (total CPS across the energy range of 0-1500 keV) and the total specific activity value. The CPS values for the γ Sniffer were extracted using Equation 2. Figure 38c illustrates the dispersion of the data, accompanied by a linear fitting analysis (indicated by the red line), yielding an equation in the following form:

$$\text{Total Specific Activity} = (60.8 \pm 11.7) \times \text{CPS Gamma Sniffer} + (8.1 \pm 68.7) \quad (3)$$

Using Eq. 3, it can be assessed the total specific activity within the effective water column detected by the γ Sniffer through integration of the count rate (0-1500 keV) recorded by the sensor. The reason for selecting the energy range (0-1500 keV) for calibrating the γ Sniffers stems from the limited volume of the CZT crystal, resulting in diminished efficiency in detecting high-energy γ -rays.

(c)

Figure 38: (a) The total specific activity as a function of the CPS integral (0-1500 keV) registered by the HPGe detector, the ratio of the CPS integral (0-1500 keV) registered by the γ Sniffer over the HPGe detector as a function of the total specific activity and (c) the total specific activity as a function of the CPS registered by the γ Sniffer.

4 Experiments at Kolumbo

Two scientific research expeditions took place from the 12th to the 15th of June 2023 and from the 20th to the 25th of October 2023 in the context of the sister project of RAMONES, SANTORY led by NKUA. The expedition was performed with the R/V AEGAEO and R/V FILIA of HCMR. Researchers from NTUA and PLOA participated in the expedition on behalf of the RAMONES consortium. The γ Sniffers, SUGI, CHERI, and CTD instruments were mounted on the HCMR ROV MaxRover and data were continuously recorded while the ROV performed RAMONES experiments and various operations related to the activities of the SANTORY project. These activities involved the recovery and re-deployment of various instruments for monitoring a number of physicochemical parameters inside the caldera of the Kolumbo volcano at 500m depth. Nine dives have been performed in total, during 13th to 14th of June and fourteen dives during 20th to 25th of October 2023.

A second expedition took place in the context of the SANTORY project from the 20th to the 25th of October again with the participation of NTUA, and PLOA on behalf of RAMONES project.

4.1 Area of work

Kolumbo submarine volcano, located 7 km northeast of the island of Santorini, is part of Santorini's volcanic complex in the south Aegean Sea, Greece. Kolumbo's last eruption was in 1650 AD causing significant damage and fatalities on the nearby island of Santorini. It is found in a small, elongated rifted basin (Anhydros Basin) within the Cyclades back-arc region of the present Hellenic subduction zone where the seafloor of the eastern Mediterranean Sea is descending beneath the Aegean microplate. The Cycladic region and the Aegean Sea are known to be regions of north-south back-arc extension and thinning of continental crust.

In 2006, a unique and active hydrothermal vent field, which degasses boiling CO₂-dominated fluids at high temperatures (~265°C) with a clear mantle signature, was revealed in the northern part of its crater floor during an oceanographic survey by remotely operated vehicles (ROVs). CTD profiles have shown pronounced anomalies directly above the active vents on Kolumbo's crater floor. Steep increases of temperature (e.g., from 16 to 19 °C) and conductivity near the maximum depth (504 m) inside Kolumbo's cone show marked spatiotemporal correlation. Vertical distributions of CTD signatures suggest a strong connection to Kolumbo's crater morphology, which is funnel shaped with a basal diameter approximately 3 km and its rim diameter about 1.7 km. The average depth of the crater rim is 150 m, whilst the shallowest lies at the depth of 18 m towards the south-western side of the volcano. The smooth crater floor is at an average depth of 500 m.

Figure 39: Christiania-Santorini-Kolumbo rift (South Aegean Sea, Greece) (Nomikou et al., 2018; Nomikou et al., 2019).

Figure 40: ROV captured photos (E/V Nautilus Leg NA-007) (Carey et al., 2011) of active high-temperature (max 265°C) Kolumbo hydrothermal sulfide mounds, vigorously discharging boiling fluids and gases (>99% CO₂) (Carey et al., 2013b; Kiliyas et al., 2013).

4.2 Participants

Table 7: List of RAMONES people participating in 1st Kolumbo expedition.

Person	Partner	Dates	Role
KARANTZALOS Konstantinos	NTUA	12/6-15/6	Team Leader
NTOUSKOS Makis	NTUA	12/6-15/6	Instruments operation/testing
ANTONIOU Christos	NTUA	12/6-15/6	Instruments operation/testing
SPANOS Sotiris	NTUA	12/6-15/6	Instruments operation/testing

Table 8: List of RAMONES people participating in 2nd Kolumbo expedition.

Person	Partner	Dates	Role
NOMIKOU Paraskevi	NKUA	20/10-24/10	Expedition leader
MALLIOS Angelos	PLOA	20/10-24/10	Instruments operation/testing
NTOUSKOS Makis	NTUA	20/10-24/10	Instruments operation/testing
ANTONIOU Christos	NTUA	20/10-24/10	Instruments operation/testing

4.3 Experiments / Infrastructure

The following instruments were used during the experiments:

- Three **γSniffers**
- **SUGI** radioactivity imaging
- **CHERI** UV imaging
- **Bentic Lab**

Control electronics of the Benthic Lab. All RAMONES instruments were connected to it, as well as to the ROV for real-time data viewing

- **CTD** conductivity, temperature, and pressure sensor (**PLOA**)
- **RadonEye** for Radon surface measurements (**PLOA**)

4.4 ROV based measurements

Deep water experiments were performed with the HCMR's "MaxRover" ROV. It is a medium working class ROV capable of operating up to 2000 m depth. The ROV was used as a carrier vehicle for facilitating measurements in different depths and near hydrothermal vents. The γ Sniffer, SUGI, and CHERI UV Camera were connected to the control module of the Benthic lab, and the last one was connected to the ROV via Ethernet. That way, there was real-time control and data through the ROV's fiber optic umbilical to the support craft.

Figure 41: SUGI and γ Sniffer instruments equipped on HCMR "MaxRover" ROV

4.5 Preliminary Results

4.5.1 First Kolumbo expedition

The radioactivity levels measured by the γ Sniffer are shown in Figure 42 for day 1 and Figure 43 for day 2, respectively. A variation up to three orders of magnitude is observed in the measured radioactivity levels which, based on the video stream and the instrument readings of the ROV, can be attributed to the proximity of the sensor to active hydrothermal vents and/or the sediments of the seabed. Nevertheless, it is interesting to note that large variations of maximum radioactivity levels are also observed between these scenarios.

Figure 42: Counts per second vs time for the data collected of the first four dives (day 1)

Figure 43: Counts per second vs time for the data collected of the last five dives (day 2)

Figure 44: Full path of the ROV from the surface, down to the vents. Most counts are registered near the vents. Here is depicted the cubic root of the 10 second measurement value. Colour indicates intensity.

Figure 45: Top 15% of the cubic root of the 10 second measurement value. Size and colour indicate intensity.

4.5.2 Second Kolumbo expedition

For this expedition the benthic lab hardware and software were suitably extended to support the simultaneous operation and joint data logging from multiple γ Sniffers. Based on these improvements, a setup with three γ Sniffers was built for continuously measuring radioactivity at different distances from the seabed (Fig. 44). Specifically, the first sniffer was placed at 0.5 m from the seabed, the second at 2 m (1.5 m from the first) and the third one at 3.5 m (1.5 m from the second). The same setup could be extended for 10 m while underwater with a purpose-built mechanism. Figure 45 shows part of the measurements captured with this setup

while deployed in the active area of the Kolumbo caldera. The setup collected data for more than 24h, 6h close to the seabed and 18h at the extended setup. The change in the radioactivity levels measured by the lowest-placed γ Sniffer before and after the unravelling can be observed in Figs. 44 and 45.

Figure 46: RAMONES team onboard of R/V Filia during 2nd expedition at Kolumbo

Figure 47: Extended-time deployment of multiple γ Sniffers in Kolumbo

Figure 48: Extended-time monitoring of radioactivity in the Kolumbo caldera captured simultaneously using three γ Sniffers placed at different depths

5 Gliders Experiments at Portugal

During the week of September 18 to 22, IST-ID, PLOA, NTUA, and EVOL gathered in Lisbon, Portugal, to test the integration of localization and communication equipment, computing, and gamma radiation sensor into the 1st RAMONES customized glider vehicle. It was the first time that equipment such as USBL-Modems from EVOL or the γ Sniffer have been installed on an underwater glider vehicle. Successful benchmarking tests were carried out at Doca dos Olivais (Fig. 49) and later glider dynamics and acoustic communications were thoroughly tested in a real environment at Castelo de Bode Dam reservoir lake (Figs. 50 and 51). Multiple short dives have been executed in the shallow waters of the lake that is 50m at its deepest point. Dive profiles (Fig. 52) suggest proper glider behaviour, paving the way for open-sea trials in the following period.

Figure 49: Full glider setup ready for test deployment at Doca dos Olivais, Lisbon, Portugal

Figure 50: Test dive at Castelo de Bode Dam reservoir lake

Figure 51: RAMONES team performing tests with underwater glider at Castelo de Bode Dam reservoir

Figure 52: Glider flight profile showing estimated depth (red) and measured pressure (blue).

6 Conclusions

This document presents a summary of all the efforts within the RAMONES project focusing on experiments performed for validation and testing of all RAMONES equipment in a relative environment. This equipment includes all instruments and vehicles that are ready for operation until M36. General guidelines are provided, describing the main role of each asset in the RAMONES system, as well as the way that their deployment and operation as a system towards radioactivity monitoring is envisioned. The document describes the full-scale campaign at Milos Island where the gamma detection instruments were thoroughly tested and validated through concurrent physical sampling. The document also presents two expeditions at the submarine volcano Kolumbo, which is the target area of deployment of the complete RAMONES system. There, the γ Sniffers, the SUGI and CHERI instruments were used to collect valuable data providing insights for the preparation of the final deployment. Finally, the document presents the experiments performed at Portugal, where the fully developed RAMONES underwater glider vehicles, equipped with the EVOL localization and acoustic systems, the RAMONES computing platform and the γ Sniffer, were tested for the first time in a real environment. The results of all these experiments provided invaluable insights, both technical and scientific, regarding radioactivity monitoring and mapping in coastal and deep-water environments, paving the way for the further development of the system as well as for the next experiments that are planned in the next period.

It is important to acknowledge the work of the external researchers that contributed to the operations and the processing of the data and the samples that were collected during the field experiments, and especially of the sister project SANTORY as by participating to the expeditions planned in its context it allowed RAMONES to gather invaluable data from the Kolumbo volcano.